

Integrating Video Apps with a Learning Management System

a review from limited Internet Access and Expensive Data Ecosystem

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Abstract

Recent economic trends have birthed several educational technologies and this can be overwhelming for Teachers and Students in this digital Era. All these new technologies have one thing in common; they support synchronous and asynchronous teaching and learning. School community must understand and accept that there are several socio-economic and technical factors that affect synchronous participation and at the top of the list is cost of data and access to internet. Therefore, the major aim of this expository paper is to create awareness of such impending online teaching data requirements and how to manage such situations without reducing the quality of teaching. Consequentially, synchronous video classes on Slack, Skype, Google Meet, Webex, YouTube Live, Google Hangout, Zoom, or Skype uses between 810 MB to 2.4 GB of data per hour and that is too expensive for participating in multiple video classes per day or in a week. However, using platforms such as Edmodo that allows controlled asynchronous required between 5MB to 110MB to participate in 2 hours of 300 students in class where an average of 310 words is posted every 10 minutes. The first section of this paper highlighted new normal trends that can push educators to adopting different e-learning systems. The second section identifies a major gap affecting the adoption of synchronous learning and the third section suggested practical approaches on Educators on the learn new ways to calibrate their course content while adopting delivery methods that will accommodate the cost and dynamics of online teaching and learning.

Keywords: Covid-19, Online-Learning, Synchronous-Learning, Asynchronous-Learning, Blended-Learning

Introduction

Today there is a surge in the use of the internet to drive several businesses as the world practices social distancing and isolation to slow the spread of the COVID19 pandemic (Lewnard & Lo, 2020). This phenomenon is bringing about a new normal, where people are utilizing existing technologies in unprecedented ways. The educational sector has not been left behind in this trend. E-learning which has been existing for some time now is becoming more and more adopted and redesigned by schools and other interested parties during this period (Murphy, 2020).

The history of e-learning can be traced back to 1997 when Maise (1997) stated that “Online Learning is the use of network technology to design, deliver, select, administer, and extend learning”. E-learning can therefore be simply defined as learning conducted with the use of electronic media. This is electronic media is usually the internet connecting student devices to their teachers. These devices could range from desktop computers to handheld mobile devices. This brings about several advantages that come with use of the internet such as scalability in the number of learners, location independence among others.

E-learning systems can be divided into two categories, Learning Management System (LMS) and Learning Content Management System (LCMS). LMS consist of functions relating to administering learning. These functions include billing, registration, scheduling of tests and other assessments etc. Whereas LCMS adds content creation or authoring of these course/subjects to the administrative functions highlighted in the LMS. Examples of LMSs include Adobe Captivate Prime, Docebo, SAP Litmos LMS, Learn Upon LMS while examples of LCMSs include moodle, Edmodo, google classroom and so on.

TYPES OF E-LEARNING SYSTEMS.

- i. Self-Study: this approach is used by students to learn certain subject they are interested in learning at their own pace. Self-study addresses the distinct learning needs, interests of individual students. (Hill et al., 2014)

- ii. Discussion Groups: These allow for peer-to-peer support and learning. Subject matter experts can add their support to the discussion to build on the peer-to-peer learning that is occurring (Selim, 2007)
- iii. Distance Education: This allows the students to self-pace through the online content. There are usually no set times frame for distance classes but students must complete the syllabus before they can get graded (Jenkins, Rumble, Murugan, et al. 2017).
- iv. Synchronous eLearning: in this approach learning the learners are learning online at the same time (Chen, 2017). With synchronous learning, participants can receive immediate feedback. Students in this approach need to be informed of the schedule prior to class time and have access to the necessary technology to engage in the online class. Synchronous Teaching usually occurs online through a live-video stream such as Slack, Skype, Google Meet, Webex, YouTube Live, Google Hangout, and Zoom. Therefore, the students can demonstrate understanding using various edtech tools available to them on Edmodo, Moodle, Schoology, and Google Classroom amongst others. Summarily Synchronous happens at the same time.
- v. Asynchronous eLearning: in this learning approach, the learners learning does not happen at the same time. In this approach the teacher uploads a short video, and lecture slides and the learners respond by sending in their questions or contribution through text or chats hence the learners are not online at the same time therefore interactions occur with some delay. With asynchronous learning, the participants can learn at their own pace (Reform, 2017).
- vi. Virtual Classroom: This is an online classroom that allows participants to communicate, view presentations, interact with learning resources and work in groups. Virtual classrooms can be used to hold lectures and tutorials online, a feature particularly useful to external students. Virtual classrooms can also be setup as online meeting spaces for students to work on group tasks (Radu, Southgate, Ortega, et al. 2017)
- vii. Audio and video conferencing: This learning approach allows the learners to use sites such as: Google Hangouts, Adobe Connect and GoTOWebinar. Webinars, or seminars held online, are modes of video conferencing. Typically, webinars are recorded for later viewing (Gault, 2017)
- viii. Blended Learning: This is a learning approach that combines both online and face-to-face delivery (Abdellatief, Sultan, Jabar, & Abdullah, 2011; Holsapple & Lee-Post, 2006; Leveaux, Gallagher, & Sixsmith, 2016). This can be seen as the method that combines both the synchronous and asynchronous learning approaches. These methods allow learners who may miss the online class learn at their own pace by following the discussions in the forum much later. These methods prefer the solution to the challenges faced in both learning methods
- ix. Flipped Learning: Flipped learning offers the ability to demonstrate content within a real-time context. This type of learning is most beneficial to students' knowledge acquisition and studying experience. Here there is a strong connection and dialogue between the students and teacher which is what empowers the students within the classroom (Lantis, Killie & Krain 2010). Even where students neglect to complete the pre-work, they are not disadvantaged as the focus of the first part of the lesson is on the 'flipped content'. This is particularly important as many academics would argue that 'most' students neglect the pre-work (Albert & Beatty, 2014). Flipped learning offers students the ability to be actively involved in the flipped component of the course if the material is delivered attractively.

RELATED WORKS

Leveaux, Gallagher, Sixsmith and Simpson (2019) examined the classroom evolution towards the adoption of blended and flipped learning methods. This study examined the fundamental problem in the classroom which has too many alternative technologies implemented. This problem does not adequately support blended learning. The main focus of eLearning information systems the blending of distance education within the classroom. This work addresses the needs of class-based teaching by designing an effective technologically

founded educational learning environment. The studies show that having online content that actively engages students both inside and outside the classroom can only occur considering the choice of the modes of content selection and delivery. Research on collaborative or blended learning has indicated student engagement to be limited at the initial stage, but in the long run flipped learning experiences and the blended learning environment in assist students in understanding threshold concepts. There is need for more studies in this area to be able to improve the learning experience of students.

Oliveira, Cunha, & Nakayama (2016) worked on a review of learning management systems (LMS) and e-learning management. E-learning is powered by Information Technology which is a component for innovation. This has provided a condition for an organization to be able to work with new businesses and improved business processes. LMS allow communication and interaction between teachers and students in virtual classroom. However, this study discovered that there are gaps concerning the use of IT for the management of e-learning systems. This work analyzes different work on how LMS for the management of e-learning was applied. LMS in e-learning management is still incipiently discussed in the literature. This analysis derives interesting characteristics from scientific studies, highlighting gaps and guidelines for future research, including learning analytics. The main contribution of this paper is related to the management of e-learning using LMS.

Cavus, Uzunboylu, and Ibrahim (2006) examined the effectiveness of using learning management systems and collaborative tools in web-based teaching of programming languages. The study was a pilot study carried out at Near East University during the 2004/5 Fall Semester using the Moodle LMS together with GREWPtool collaborative editor. In this work a system was developed and tested with 36 students taking the Java and the Pascal programming courses. The outcome of this study shows that using a Learning Management System is not efficient if it is not enhanced by a collaborative learning tool. Also teaching programming languages such as Pascal and Java is thought successfully in a web-based environment using an LMS together with a collaborative tool.

Henry (2014) worked on using mobile apps and social media for generating contents for online learner. In this work an evolutionary approach to extending and enhancing the online learning experience for adult students in the LMS-based online college was examined by introducing the use of mobile phones and the social media platform for learning activities. However, due to the vast adoption of mobile devices with data plans still evolving, a model that can integrate mobile learning activities into the online course assignments allowing them to use various resources with their mobile devices as a means of creating learner-generated content and sharing communications about that process was developed. The model was tested and proven to work effectively kin generating learning content. The outcome of this work helps to identify useful social media and mobile apps for mobile learning, providing examples of their successful integration into online course assignments and activities, and propose methods of further research and development.

Sailer, Kiefer, and Raubal (2015) examined on an integrated learning management system for location-based mobile learning. In this work the relevance and challenges of a location-based learning platform that supports mobile learning in education was presented. The design of an integrated management system for location-based mobile learning was achieved in this work. Independent of the taught subject, the objective of the system is an easy-to-understand user interface for both - teachers and students to use for teaching and learning.

Du, Fu, Zhao, Liu and Liu (2013) worked on Interactive and Collaborative E-Learning Platform with Integrated Social Software and Learning Management System. In this work it was established that e-learning introduces collaboration between leaners and educators which is important for both learners and educators. While learning management system (LMS) is the traditional approach to e-learning which is organized as courses; social software including blogs, wikis, social networking sites, and social bookmarking sites amongst others are adopted by many educators to meet their emerging needs in educations. This work proposed an interactive and collaborative e-learning platform which combines the advantages of LMS and social software by integrating social software with LMS which will help satisfy the needs for participation, interaction, and collaboration of

learners and educators. The platform connects course network of users with their social network and knowledge network. As a result, it is helpful to users in building their personalized social network and knowledge network during the process of learning. But within all these works, a gap still remains unfilled and that is how do we manage data plan and accommodate students who may not have ready access to an internet.

Integrating Video App with a Learning Management Systems (LMS)

OFFERING A BLENDING LEARNING ENVIRONEMT

Teachers and Students are overwhelmed by new teaching and learning technologies in this digital Era. All these new technologies have one thing in common; they support synchronous and asynchronous teaching and learning. Summarily, Synchronous happens at the same time while Asynchronous does not happen at the same time. With synchronous learning, participants can receive immediate feedback. With asynchronous learning, the participants can learn at their own pace.

For a synchronous online learning experience, you need to determine the content and schedule of the experience. Students need to be informed of the schedule prior to class time and have access to the necessary technology to engage in the online class. Synchronous Teaching will occur online via a live-video stream such as Slack, Skype, Google Meet, Webex, YouTube Live, Google Hangout, Zoom, or Skype. Students can demonstrate understanding using various edtech tools available to them on Edmodo, Moodle, Schoology, and Google Classroom and so on. Several Factors (Socioeconomic or Technical) informs or influences Teaching And Learning Experiences and Data is one of the most important factors. Students are located in different regions and this presents connectivity issues, with student and teachers in rural areas unable to connect to mobile hotspots and cellular service from their homes

Data usage and Online Learning

In 2020, the lowest video quality setting on video apps such as Slack, Skype, Google Meet, Google Hangout or Zoom, hosting a class of 30 participants (students) and above via video will take nothing below 13.5 MB and 40 MB per minute that which ranges from 810 MB to 2.4 GB per hour of your class. According to Reviews.org (2020) and AT & T Universal Data Calculator (2019-2020), “the more participants in the video-enabled class, the more the data you will use”. Examples data usage can be found in table 1-3

Table 1:

Day-to-day Activities and default amount Data Consumed

Activity	Amount of data used
4K video streaming	5.85 GB/hr.
HD video streaming	2.5 GB/hr.
SD video streaming	0.7 GB/hr.
Audio streaming	72 MB/hr.
Uploading one image to social media	5 MB/photo
Sending emails (without attachment)	20 KB/email
Sending emails (with standard attachment)	300 KB/email
Online gaming	12 MB/hr.
Viewing a web page	1 MB/pg.

Table 2:

Zoom data usage for a 1:1 meeting

Quality	Download	Upload	Total
High	270 MB/hr.	270 MB/hr.	540 MB/hr.
720p	540 MB/hr.	540 MB/hr.	1.08 GB/hr.
1080p	810 MB/hr.	810 MB/hr.	1.62 GB/hr.

Table 3:

Zoom data usage for a group call

Quality	Download	Upload	Total
High	450 MB/hr.	360 MB/hr.	810 MB/hr.
720p	675 MB/hr.	675 MB/hr.	1.35 GB/hr.
1080p	1.2 GB/hr.	1.2 GB/hr.	2.4 GB/hr.

You use somewhere between 540 MB and 1.62 GB per hour (between 9 MB and 27 MB per minute) for a 1:1 Zoom meeting, depending upon the streaming quality.

Managing the data consumption

There is a way to reduce to data required to run your classes and it is called Blended Learning (BL). In this paper we represent BL as a pedagogical approach which given by

$$\text{WEIGHTED SYNCHRONOUS} + \text{CONTROLLED ASYNCHRONOUS} = \text{BLENDED LEARNING}$$

In a Weighted Synchronous Learning, the lecturer must filter some major Topics from the Course Outline that requires a face-to-face video presence before the impact can be felt by the students.

In a Controlled Asynchronous Learning, the lecturer uploads scheduled texts, pre-recorded short videos clips or audio, and then allows students to respond and interact using texts and chats within the class period. Students who were not able to join real-time due to technical or other issues beyond their control are given opportunities to learn without locking them out completely.

CASE STUDY BLENDING EDMODO AND ZOOM

ZOOM	EDMODO
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. You connect synchronously with your students over video (if bandwidth allows), audio, screen sharing, poll, and text chat. 2. You can put students to work in groups, either when you enable breakout rooms for them, or when they use their personal meeting rooms to meet with peers. 3. You can to create a simple “screencast” (for example, recording voice-over presentations) and share it with your students. 4. The ability to use written annotations on a whiteboard or directly onto documents on your screen when sharing. 5. Using a tablet with a stylus or writing implement] to annotate will allow for advanced annotation, such as writing out mathematical formulas. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. You can connect to anyone who is within your school and Department Groups 2. You can create smaller groups for specific students such as Carryover students, Direct-Entry, “Late Resumers” and even Project Groups 3. Share class resources such as websites, embedded YouTube clips, flipped task links, files, documents and images with students and co-teachers. You can then preschedule pop up notes and texts, allowing to teach and grade from anywhere and at anytime. 4. Enforce learning and participation with direct message students means that I can give them feedback privately. This can include feedback about academic results or behavior 5. Organize your gradebook viewable by you, your students and their parents

For data usage rates and attention span sake try to keep your videos below 40minutes. Even if you have license to stream for 24hours. For pre-recorded video uploads on Edmodo, keep these videos/audios below 15 mins; using a text-based asynchronous will require between 10MB to 150MB to participate in 2 hours class where at least 300 words is to posted in 10 minutes

Steps to setup a data friendly online classes using zoom and or Edmodo**Step 1:**

Know the topics that must require a face-to-face explanation or annotations. Start your Zoom and Edmodo and share screen

Step 2:

Know the topics that must require a face-to-face explanation or annotations. Start your Zoom and Edmodo and share screen

Step 3:

Observe the same netiquette as indicated in Edmodo even on zoom, example: you can make class representative to be the Co-host, mute every participant (you may allow them to unmute themselves during question and answer time).

Step 4: Disable annotations by participants to avoid them drawing all over the screen why you are teaching.

Step 5:

You can be split your PC screen into two, and see both Edmodo and Zoom at the same time without having to minimize. I will show you how in later slides

Step 6:

Emphasize learning and delivery by using the breakout room

Know the topics that must require a face-to-face explanation or annotations. Start your Zoom and Edmodo and share screen

Figure 1: Showing a video-enabled and shared-screen classroom (breakout session)

Make sure you take attendance during your class. For Edmodo always start with an attendance. You can also take attendance on Zoom using the Poll feature for zoom, you can take attendance after your class preliminaries however make those using zoom all joined with their full names. Edmodo will allow you students to do both real time attendance and for those who joined later to also take their attendance unlike Zoom Attendance which must be real time only

Figure 2: Snapshot showing attendance sessions on Edmodo (Controlled Asynchronous) and Zoom (Synchronous)

Note: Edmodo Attendance can be controlled for the students who due to connectivity may not be online while the attendance is on. So, the Edmodo Attendance is used to cushion the issue of marking the student completely absent for the whole day or week. Unlike in Zoom where “End Poll” will capture only the respondent’s Full name for further exporting into an external spreadsheet. How to setup poll as attendance is not covered in this paper

Figure 3: Snapshot showing Breakout Section on Zoom

Setting up your class via split views in Windows 10

Step 1: Once you are logged in. drag and drop your zoom window into the corner you want to snap it to. Alternatively, press the windows key arrow left or right arrow, followed by up and down

Step 2: Do the same with Edmodo (web browser) on the same side and you will have two snapped windows into place for a better view

Step 3: After your zoom class, copies of recorded videos on zoom can be added as study-at-your pace materials for those who many have internet connection or data issues

Figure 4: Snapshot showing splitting of Zoom and Edmodo in one PC
In older version of Windows (8,7 and below)

Step 1:

Hold down your left click and carry your zoom window.

Step 2: Drag the open window to any of the edges of your PC Screen till it gives you a showed reflect as show above. Then release the zoom

Step 3: Repeat same thing as you did in zoom. Hold down your left click and carry your web browser (firefox, chrome, internet explorer). Hit the open window to any of the edges of your PC Screen till it gives you a showed reflect as show above. Then release the browser

Figure 5: Snapshot showing split but paned Zoom and Edmodo in one PC

Splitting your Screen in Mac Systems

Step 1: Hover your pointer over the full-screen button in the upper-left corner of a window. Or click and hold the button. Step 2: Choose “Tile Window to Left of Screen” or ”Tile Window to Right of Screen” from the menu. ... Step 3: Click a window on the other side of the screen to begin using both windows side by side.

Additional Information on Sharing of Audio

Allowing your student to hear the sound of video clips (e.g movies from VLC) or an audio from your computer. Click on share screen and select share computer sound. Selecting Optimize screen share will take less data, but will reduce the quality of the video that you are about to share

Figure 6: Enabling audio and optimizing screen share

Figure 7: Showing Prescheduled Text-based classes posts and also recorded videos of the interaction available as asynchronous playable material

Conclusion and Recommendation

Online Classes presents a lot of benefits both for teachers and learning. However, the world of online teaching has impending challenge which is the availability of data and access to steady internet. But knowing how to manage data consumption can improve the level at which online classes are received by student and parents. One practical way to reduce to data required to run your classes by adopting a weight synchronous and controlled asynchronous teaching and learning (called Blended Learning). To improve the level of benefits, Educators should filter out major Topics from the Course Outline that requires a face-to-face video presence before the impact can be felt by the students and then use a controlled Asynchronous Learning platform to uploads scheduled notes or texts which costs way less as compared to video classes. Addon to prescheduled text-based, pre-recorded short videos clips or audio, allows students to respond and interact using texts and chats within the class period. Students who were not able to join real-time due to technical or other issues beyond their control are given opportunities to learn without locking them out completely.

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